

Digital Payments and Financial Growth in India: A Study of UPI and Financial Inclusion

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1. Abstract:

India is a progressive country and is rapidly moving towards digital development. With the emerging of digital technology, its influence has also been observed in developing country like India. And its impact is clearly visible in the Indian Financial Sector. At present, people rarely carry loose cash in their pockets, yet they continue to perform financial transactions easily. Much of the credit for this transformation should be given to the **Unified Payments Interface (UPI)** platform, which provides digital payment services. Among the various digital payment platforms, UPI has emerged as the most widely used system for instant money transfer. Researcher examine the relationship between digital payments, financial growth, and financial inclusion in India. The study is based on purely secondary data which is collected from government reports, banking statistics, and various research publications. The findings indicate that digital payment platforms, particularly UPI, have significantly increased financial transactions, improved access to banking various services, and promoted financial inclusion. However, challenges such as digital illiteracy, cyber-security risks, and infrastructure limitations still affect the smooth adoption of digital payments where the people of India are not literate well in some areas. The study concludes that digital payments are a key driver of financial growth and play.

Keywords: Digital Payments, Financial Growth, UPI & its Applications, Financial Inclusion, Digital Economy.

1. Introduction:

A major transformation has taken place in the financial sector due to the integration of digital technology in banking and payment systems. It can be observed that traditional cash-based transaction methods are gradually declining and are being replaced by electronic payment methods that are faster, safer, and more convenient. Digital payment systems include internet banking, mobile banking, debit and credit cards, electronics wallets, and real-time payment platforms. The Government of India has actively promoted the use of digital payments through initiatives such as the Digital India programme and financial inclusion schemes. These initiatives aim to reduce

dependence on cash and encourage citizens to adopt electronic payment methods. The development of digital infrastructure, widespread smartphone usage, and increased internet connectivity have also contributed to the growth of payments of digitals. Among the various digital payment systems, the **Unified Payments Interface (UPI)** has emerged as a revolutionary platform. It is observed that many users prefer using mobile applications to transfer money instantly, as it is very simple and convenient. This system has made financial transactions easier and has expanded access to financial services for millions of people. As a result, digital payments have become an important factor in India's financial growth and economic development.

2. Objectives:

1. To understand the concept and development of digital payments in India.
2. To study the various types of UPI Applications.
3. To analyse the role of UPI in the growth of digital financial transactions.
4. To examine the contribution of digital payments to financial inclusion.
5. To identify the challenges associated with digital payments system in India.

3. Research Methodology:

In this research paper researcher focus on secondary data which is collected from various reliable sources such as, Reports of the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), Publications of the National Payments Corporation of India (NPCI), Government reports and economic surveys, Research journals, books, and academic articles, official websites and financial statistics databases. The collected information has been analysed by researcher using a descriptive and analytical approach to understand the relationship between digital payments and financial growth in India.

4. Concept of Digital Payments:

Electronic or cashless payments enable you to use money digitally without need for liquid cash.¹ Digital payments refer to financial transactions conducted electronically without the use of physical cash. These transactions are processed through digital devices such as mobile phones, computers, and payment terminals. Digital payment systems provide several advantages including convenience, speed, security, and transparency.

In our country the digital payments ecosystem includes multiple platforms such as internet banking, mobile wallets, debit and credit cards, point-of-sale terminals, and UPI-based applications. These system allow individuals and business to transfer funds/cash quickly and efficiently. Digital

¹ <https://www.axis.bank.in/blogs/digital-banking/what-is-digital-payment>

payments reduce the dependency on physical cash and contribute to the development of a cashless or less-cash economy. They also improve financial transparency by creating digital records of transaction.

In short digital payment means there is no need for physical money. People from anywhere can buy and sell things easily with the help of UPI platforms.

5. Growth of UPI in India:

The Unified Payments Interface (UPI) was launched by the National Payments Corporation of India (NPCI) in 2016 with the objective of simplifying digital transactions. UPI allows users to send or receive money instantly through mobile applications linked to their bank accounts. Since its introduction, UPI has experienced remarkable growth in India. The platform has gained popularity due to its simplicity, speed, and cost-effectiveness. Users can perform transactions at any time without visiting to branch of the banks.

UPI has also encouraged the development of various mobile payment applications used by individuals, businesses, and merchants. These applications have made digital payments easily accessible even too small retailers and street vendors. Several mobile applications in India operate on the **Unified Payments Interface (UPI)** framework, enabling instant and secure financial 6transactions. The major UPI platforms in India are as follows,

1. **MobiKwik-** This launch as a mobile wallet (2009) platform and later integrated UPI .Services, enabling users to perform money transfer, wallet payments, and bill payments.

2. **Paytm-** started as a digital wallet and mobile recharge platform. It later integrated UPI services in 2017, allowing users to perform instant bank-to-bank transfers.
3. **PhonePe-** (2016) was among the earliest applications to adopt UPI technology, offering services such as money transfer, bill payments, insurance purchases, and investments.
4. **BHIM-**Bharat Interface for Money (2016) was launched by the National Payments Corporation of India to promote digital payments and simplify UPI-based transactions.
5. **Google Pay-**Initially introduced as *Tez* in India, Google Pay (2017) enables instant money transfer, QR-code payments, bill payments, and mobile recharges.
6. **Amazon Pay-** (2017) was integrated with the Amazon platform and later added UPI functionality to support online and offline payments.
7. **Cred-**(2018) started as a credit card bill payment platform and later introduced UPI services for instant financial transactions.
8. **WhatsApp Pay-**(2020) allows users to send and receive money directly within the messaging application using UPI technology.

6. Digital Payments and Financial Inclusions:

Digital payment platforms, particularly UPI, have significantly strengthened financial inclusion in India by improving access to banking services, reducing transaction costs, enabling credit access, and supporting inclusive economic growth.

1. Expansion of Access to Banking Services.
2. Reduction in transaction Cost.
3. Growth of Digital transaction in India
4. Financial History and Credit Access.
5. Promotion of Financial Inclusion for Small Merchants.
6. Supports for Government Welfare Scheme.
7. Empowerment of Women and Marginalised Groups.
8. Growth in Financial Inclusion Index.

Table No. 1 : Growth of UPI transactions and Financial Inclusions		
Year	UPI Transactions (Amount in Billion)	Impact of Financial Inclusion.
2018	0.9	Early Stage Adoption
2019	5.4	Increasing Digital Awareness

2020	12.5	Rapid Adoption during Pandemic
2021	38.7	Expansion to Small Merchants
2022	74	Strong Growth in Rural Transactions
2023	117	Mass Adoption Across Sector
2024-2025	228	Digital Payment Integrated into daily life
Source: Reserve Bank of India, National Payments Corporation of India Reports.		

8. Impacts of Digital Payments and Financial Growth:

The Reserve Bank of India (RBI) has been publishing the Reserve Bank of India – Digital Payments Index (RBI-DPI) since January 1, 2021, with March 2018 as the base period, to measure the extent of digitalisation of payments across the country. The index serves as an important indicator to assess the growth and adoption of digital payment systems in India. According to RBI data, the value of the Digital Payments Index for September 2025 reached 516.76, compared to 493.22 in March 2025, which was announced on July 28, 2025. This steady increase in the index reflects the rapid expansion and wider adoption of digital payment mechanisms across the country. The growth in the RBI-DPI has been mainly driven by significant improvements in parameters such as Payment Performance and Payment Enablers, including the increasing use of digital platforms, mobile payment applications, and improved payment infrastructure. The rising index value indicates that digital payment systems are becoming an integral part of India’s financial ecosystem and are contributing significantly to the development of a digitally empowered economy.²

The Index Series since its inception is as under:

² https://rbi.org.in/scripts/BS_PressReleaseDisplay.aspx?prid=62213

The Reserve Bank of India – Digital Payments Index (RBI-DPI) measures the growth and adoption of digital payment systems in India. The base year for the index is March 2018 = 100, which represents the starting level of digital payment development in the country.

The Bar Graph and Figure 2 the **steady and continuous growth of the RBI Digital Payments Index from 2018 to September 2025**. Starting from the **base value of 100 in March 2018**, the index **increased to 153.47 in March 2019** and further to **173.49 in September 2019**, indicating the early expansion of digital payment usage. During **2020, the index rose to 207.84 in March and 217.74 in September**, reflecting increased adoption of digital payments, especially during the pandemic period when contactless transactions became more common.

The growth continued strongly in the following years. In **2021, the index reached 270.59 in March and 304.06 in September**, showing **wider acceptance** of digital payment platforms such as **Unified Payments Interface (UPI)** and mobile banking services. By 2022, the index further increased to 349.3 in March and 377.46 in September, indicating rapid growth in digital payment infrastructure and usage.

In 2023, the RBI-DPI rose to 395.57 in March and 418.77 in September, reflecting the growing popularity of digital transactions among individuals and businesses. The upward trend continued in 2024, reaching 445.5 in March and 465.33 in September.

Finally, in **2025**, the index recorded **493.22** in March and increased to **516.76** in September, showing a significant expansion of digital payment systems across the country.

9. Challenges of Digital Payment System:

Despite the rapid growth of digital payment systems in India, several challenges such as digital illiteracy, cyber-security risks, poor internet connectivity, and lack of infrastructure continue to hinder their widespread adoption.

1. Digital Illiteracy

Many people, especially in rural areas, lack adequate knowledge and skills to use digital payment platforms effectively.

2. Cyber-security Threats

As we heard number of times about the digital frauds and its types such as hacking, phishing, and identity theft pose significant risk to digital payment users.

3. Poor Internet Connectivity

In many remote and rural areas, unstable internet connectivity-often limited to **2G or 3G networks**-creates difficulties in completing digital transactions. Poor network quality may

lead to transaction failures, and in some cases the transferred amount may remain temporarily locked or delayed for a few days before it is successfully reversed or processed.

4. Lack of Digital Infrastructure

Insufficient digital infrastructure, including limited network coverage and lack of digital devices, affects the smooth functioning of digital payments.

5. Privacy and Data Security Concern

Users often worry about the misuse of personal and financial data stored on digital platforms.

6. Technical Failures

Server downtime, application crashes, and transaction failures can disrupt digital payment systems.

7. Limited Awareness Among Users

Many individuals are not fully aware of the features, benefits, and safe usage practices of digital payment applications.

8. Trust Issues

Some users still prefer cash transactions due to lack of trust in digital payment systems.

9. Risk of Financial Frauds

Unauthorised transactions and fake payment links can result in financial losses for users.

10. Dependence on Smartphones and Technology

UPI Transactions are totally dependent on smartphones and its operating technology.

11. High Cost of Digital Devices

The cost of smartphones and internet services can be a barriers for economically weaker sections in our country.

12. Limited Acceptance by Small Merchants

Although increasing, some small business and vendors still hesitate to adopt digital payments methods.

13. Power Supply Issue

We envision a develop India by 2047; however, even today electricity has not reached many parts of our country. In places where electricity is available, the number of hours for which power is supplied remains a serious concern. Therefore this situation can be considered one of the major challenges.

14. Language Barriers

Many digital payment applications primarily operate in English, making it difficult for regional language users, now some of application's are providing regional languages for better payment by the users.

15. Regulatory and Compliance Challenges

As many of time we heard that banks are not responsible any issue with PhonePe or Google Pay because this application are not the authenticate application from any nationalised banks for schedule banks.

10. Findings:

1. Digital payment systems have significantly increased financial transactions in India.
2. UPI has become one of the most widely used digital payment platforms in all ages but especially teenage more prefer this.
3. Digital payments have improved financial inclusion by expanding access to banking digital services.
4. Electronic transactions promote transparency and efficiency in the financial system which cut the frauds and many more things related to such activities.
5. Challenges such as cyber-security threats and digital literacy gaps still exist.

11. Conclusion:

Digital payments have become a vital component of India's modern financial system. The development of UPI and other electronic payment platforms has transformed the way financial transactions are conducted. These technologies have made financial services more accessible, efficient, and transparent.

Digital payments have also supported financial inclusion by connecting millions of individuals and businesses to the formal financial system. However, to ensure sustainable growth, policymakers must address challenges related to cybersecurity, digital literacy, and technological infrastructure. With continued innovation and supportive government policies, digital payment systems are expected to play a crucial role in strengthening India's financial growth and digital economy in the future.

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